

FEATURES ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT EDUCATIONAL ACTIVITY OF PRIMARY GRADE TEACHERS

Norboeva S.M.

Gulistan State University, Senior lecturer

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14680387>

Abstract. *Pedagogical and psychological factors influencing the development of the educational activities of future primary school teachers and their impact characteristics were discussed.*

Keywords: *primary school teacher, educational activity, correlational, psychological training, pedagogical and psychological factor.*

Although many modern scientific studies have been conducted and solutions have been developed in world higher education institutions and scientific and practical centers dedicated to improving the quality of education and developing educational activities, the study of the specific mechanisms of educational activities and the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of developing the educational activities of future primary school teachers remains relevant. In this regard, there is a need to pay special attention to research aimed at using modernized methods of education, forming an intellectual generation by strengthening its intellectual potential, and organizing education by changing the educational conditions of educational institutions.

In order to understand the educational and scientific foundations of the educational and scientific activity of future elementary school teachers, studies devoted to the problems of creative thinking are considered important. The phenomenon of creativity is considered by scientists in various approaches: as a feature of reflection; as a specific type of formation and development in the dialectical interpretation of creativity; as a specific process in the synergetic interpretation of creativity; as the basis of development, movement, change (Ya.A. Ponomarev and others). The category of creativity and creative potential surfaced as leading categories in the scientific research of M.S.Kagan and others. Creativity has been extensively studied by J.Guilford, C.Rogers, and others.

Psychologists F.Genov, L.A.Korostleva, M.V.Kroz, O.S.Sovetova and others have addressed the emergence of psychological barriers to innovation in the context of general innovation and the complex provision of innovations, and have also based their work on the tasks of forming positive norms, that is, the role of educational and scientific norms.

The task of mass preparation of future elementary school teachers for educational and scientific activities, especially in scientific fields, remains very relevant today. Educational and scientific activities have a complex structure: they are the inseparable result of many interconnected processes, and they should be considered in all their aspects. However, its core is a unique educational and scientific mindset that serves all stages of the development and implementation of innovations and ensures their high-quality, effective, and practical application. Such thinking rarely emerges on its own. Typically, it is formed in a favorable environment that stimulates thinking processes over a long period of time, therefore, preparing young people for academic and scientific activity and shaping their thinking should be implemented as soon as possible, starting from school. The concept of "academic and scientific thinking" along with the terms "academic and scientific activity", "innovation" has been frequently encountered in various

sources in recent years.

Yu.N.Kulyutkin calls the motivation of a person for social prestige the motivation of indirect knowledge.

In this case, another system of motives becomes a means of cognitive activity: they express the need for a person to express himself, to preserve and affirm his "I". Here there is no utilitarian benefit for the person himself, there is a possibility of achieving self-affirmation as an individual within a certain social group.

K.Lewin, a representative of the Gestalt school of psychology, based on the method of experimental study of motives, came to the conclusion that the motive reigns absolutely independently. No matter how the category of image is understood in Gestalt psychology, K.Lewin uses the motive in his "field (space) theory" as such a category. The constants of personality and personality traits of behavior are not taken into account. K.Lewin, unlike Z.Freud, made his contribution to the development of existing doctrine by experimentally examining motives in the context of the organism-environment system. In his theory, motivation has an innate (natural) and acquired (morally acquired) form, the first of which is more characteristic of animals, the second of which is more characteristic of humans. Due to the lack of a thorough explanation of the important laws inherent in the motive and its dependence on relevant factors, K.Lewin's ideas remain controversial to this day.

Z.Freud interprets the laws of the motive only in terms of a dynamic energy state. According to a group of foreign psychologists, the motive is the energy side of experiences and reactions.

G.Allport advanced the idea of applying an approach focused on the formation and social essence of the personality in the study of the essence of human motivation. In his theory of self-actualization, the personality is analyzed as a subject of motivation. In his concept of personality, he interpreted the personality as a "motivational system" and divided the motive into lower (biological needs) and higher (spiritual development) levels. Allport emphasizes that motives are central to the individual, but he neglects the close connection between moral motives and socio-historical conditions. Based on the theory of expectations of Canadian psychologist Victor Broom, the factors (motives) that motivate a person to achieve something are not the only condition for achieving it. A person should think that the actions he chooses will lead to the satisfaction of his own needs. A person's actions are always related to choosing between two or more options. And what he does and how he does it depends on what he chooses. In other words, according to the "Broom" theory, motivation depends on how much a person wants and how much he has the opportunity, how much effort he is ready to make for this.

Broom's theory of expectations and its application has very good results in practice. It is very useful for strengthening the motivation of employees in organizations and the activities of managers at various levels.

In the equity theory of American psychologist John Stacey Adams, a person evaluates the effectiveness of motivation not by some factors, but by taking into account the calculations and results obtained by other people in other conditions. That is, motivation is viewed not from the point of view of a person's needs, but rather in comparison with others. Here, subjective evaluations are used, that is, people compare the results of their own efforts with the efforts of others and their results. And here, equality (justice) is manifested in five options: insufficient evaluation, fair evaluation, and overevaluation.

The complex theory of motivation of American psychologists Lehman Porter and Edward Lawler is characterized by the incorporation of elements of Broom's expectancy theory and Adams's theory of justice. This model has five parameters: effort expended, intelligence, results obtained, reward, and satisfaction. According to this theory, outcomes depend on a person's directed actions, abilities, and personality traits, as well as their sense of self. The level of effort determines the value of the reward and the degree of confidence that the actions taken will lead to a particular reward. Here, too, a person satisfies his needs with a reward for achieving a certain result.

If all the components of the Porter-Lawler theory are studied in detail, analyzed, and analyzed, then it becomes possible to understand the mechanism of motivation at a higher level. The efforts expended by a person depend on how valuable the achievement is to him and on the person's belief in his relationships. Achieving certain results ensures a person's satisfaction and self-esteem.

In conclusion, the problems of the level structure of the sphere of personal motivation, together with the above-mentioned problems, are directly related to him. Problems of the hierarchical structure of mental phenomena are widespread in psychology and are still being applied today, but this is not without reason, because the given ideas about the hierarchical structure make it possible to create models of mental phenomena brought into a certain system. The existence of motivational states that vary in their level and complexity in the field of individual motivation creates the conditions for the effective use of various ideas about the hierarchical structure in this area.

REFERENCES

1. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidentining 2019-yil 8-oktabrdagi PF-5847-sonli farmoni «O‘zbekiston Respublikasi oliy ta‘lim tizimini 2030 yilgacha rivojlantirish konsepsiyasini tasdiqlash to‘g‘risida».
2. Mirziyoyev SH.M. Erkin va farovon, demokratik O‘zbekiston davlatini birgalikda barpo etamiz. O‘zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti lavozimiga kirishish tantanali marosimiga bag‘ishlangan Oliy Majlis palatalarining qo‘shma majlisidagi nutq. – T.: O‘zbekiston, 2017. - 56 b.
3. Ломов Б.Ф. // Фундаментальные и прикладные исследования современной психологии: результаты и перспективы развития. – М.: Изд-во «Институт психологии РАН», 2017. – 2704 с. С. 61-68.
4. Davletshin M.G. va boshqalara. Yosh davrlari va pedagogik psixologiya / O‘quv metodik qo‘llanma. Toshkent 2004. 129 b.
5. Karimova V.M., Akramova F.A. Psixologiya: Ma‘ruzalar matni - TDIU, 2005 - 210 b.
6. Davletshin M.G. Zamonaviy maktab o‘quvchicining psixologiyasi. T., O‘zbekiston.- 2001. 30 b.
7. Давыдов, В.В. Научное обеспечение образования в свете нового педагогического мышления / В.В. Давыдов // Новое педагогическое мышление. -М., 2009. 99 С.